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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities carried out during the four years of the ARIADNEplus project on the implementation of the ARIADNEplus Ontology within Task 4.4 of Work Package 4 (WP4). Other Tasks of WP4, including the operation of the help desk, the procedure for mapping datasets to the data model and supporting the 3M mapping tool, and the integration of digital libraries were reported in Deliverable D4.3. Related work has taken place under WP2 (Extending and Supporting the ARIADNE community), WP5 (Extending the ARIADNEplus data infrastructure), WP12 (data integration and interoperability), and WP14 (The ARIADNEplus knowledge management system), and these provide the focus of other deliverables (D2.5, D5.4, D12.5, and D14.2).

The overall objective of WP4 was to Integrate the datasets of the Archaeological Research Communities, and Task 4.4 was focussed on Implementing the ARIADNE ontology - the AO-Cat - and the ontology extensions, known as application profiles, to specific sub-domains of archaeology and archaeological science. The work was organised in subtasks by domain. In this report we finalise the presentation of the AO-Cat in Section 3. The outcome of progress on each of the fourteen potential application profiles is reported in Section 4. In Deliverable D4.2 we presented three case studies in detail (for Heritage Science, Bio-Archaeology and Ancient DNA, and Inscriptions). In Section 5 of this deliverable we present one further case study for Fieldwork activities, an extensive investigation of how the ARIADNE Ontology can be used to model particularly complex and articulated scenarios of archaeological investigations and activities.

The results achieved by Task 4.4 (in collaboration with WP14) have gone far beyond the expectations framed at the beginning of the project. Indeed, the development process of the application profiles and their systematisation as part of the general ARIADNE ontological framework have not only allowed the efficient and complete representation of the entire ARIADNE information ecosystem, but have also greatly contributed to the advancement of research in the field of the development of ontologies and conceptual models for cultural heritage. Of particular note was the development of the AO-Cat, a completely new standard that allowed us to construct the ARIADNE Catalogue in an effective and straightforward way, and to achieve an outstanding level of integration of over three million archaeological resources encompassing all sub-domains. The AO-Cat has proved to be perfectly adequate and sufficient for modelling data on palaeo-anthropology (subtask 4.4.1), maritime and underwater archaeology (subtask 4.4.11) and for most of the information in the domains of environmental archaeology (subtask 4.4.3) and public archaeological finds (subtask 4.4.7), in which the extensive use of controlled vocabularies to assign specific concepts to each of the defined instances has also allowed to reach a particularly extensive level of integration. The fact that a slightly modified version of the AO-Cat is now proving itself fit for purpose for data aggregation of maritime heritage data drawn from all of the constituent nations of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland demonstrates its applicability to projects beyond ARIADNE. The AO-Cat has also proved to be efficient in combination with the extensions of the CIDOC CRM ecosystem used for field survey information (subtask 4.4.6 in combination with CRMarchaeo), standing structures (subtask 4.4.9, in interaction with CRMba) and inscriptions (subtask 4.4.13 together with CRMtex). In some cases it was sufficient to combine AO-Cat with a specialised service, such as that of spatio-temporal

data (subtask 4.4.10) set up for interoperability of geographical information, to achieve optimal integration without any need to define additional dedicated conceptual tools.

Among the new models, in addition to the AO-Cat, the development of the application profile for scientific data (CRMhs, for subtasks 4.4.4 and 4.4.5) and for bio-archaeology and ancient DNA (subtask 4.4.2) was also of considerable interest. These are two entirely new models, harmonised with each other, and devoted to the study of the specific problems of heritage science. The classes and properties introduced by these models have also proved to be of great use in other subdomains. In fact, one of the most interesting strategies adopted in the development phase was the reuse of models previously defined in ARIADNEplus, (CRMhs and aDNA in particular) for the definition of subsequent application profiles, such as those for remote sensing (subtask 4.4.8) and burials (4.4.14). In this case, the conceptual foundations and the logic with which the reused entities had previously been defined in the original ontologies have also been taken up and adapted to the rationales of the new models. A very sophisticated case was that of fieldwork activity (task 4.4.12), where the complexity of the domain and of the multiple events and activities that it involves required the deployment of most of the ARIADNE Ontology models alongside CRMarchaeo for the development of the application profile,

The definition of such an assorted and well-orchestrated set of ontological models is an extraordinary achievement for a project like ARIADNEplus which has put integration and interoperability at the heart of its research programme. Beyond their immediate usefulness for the construction of the ARIADNE semantic data space, the importance of this development work lies in the ability to conceptually model the infinite facets of a complex domain such as that of archaeology. The application profiles are innovative tools, ready to be used in external contexts, as an effective standard for the information of other research domains. The ARIADNE Ontology is squarely placed in the family of CIDOC CRM ontologies, which it enriches and with which it forms a synergistic system for modelling any type of information produced by the domains of Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science.

2 Introduction and Objectives

This deliverable updates Deliverable D4.2 and describes the activities carried out during the four years of the ARIADNEplus project¹ on the implementation of the ARIADNEplus Ontology within Task 4.4 of Workpackage 4 (WP4). Other Tasks of WP4, including the operation of the help desk, the procedure for mapping datasets to the data model and supporting the 3M mapping tool, and the integration of digital libraries were reported in Deliverable D4.3.

Related work also took place under WP2 (Extending and Supporting the ARIADNE community), WP5 (Extending the ARIADNEplus data infrastructure), WP12 (data integration and interoperability), and WP14 (The ARIADNEplus knowledge management system), and these provide the focus of other deliverables (D2.5, D5.4, D12.5, and D14.2).

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¹ The ARIADNEplus project is the continuation of ARIADNE, which established the methodology and started creating the community. We use *ARIADNEplus project* or simply *ARIADNEplus* to indicate the work done in the current project and *ARIADNE* to denote the shared vision and methodology, as for example in the sentence ‘ARIADNEplus relies on the ARIADNE community’ which refers to the community created by the ARIADNE project and has been extended by ARIADNEplus. Reference to the former ARIADNE project results, activities, etc are denoted by explicitly referencing the ‘project’ e.g. ‘ARIADNEplus extends the scope of the ARIADNE project’. In sum, *ARIADNE* refers to the common philosophy of *ARIADNEplus* (project) and of the former *ARIADNE project*.

3 The AO-Cat Ontology for the ARIADNE Catalogue

The ARIADNE Ontology, AO for short, is an ontology for the archaeological domain that has been developed by the ARIADNEplus project for the purpose of integrating the archaeological data of the ARIADNE partners into a common information space, according to the following methodology. First, a standard ontology in the Cultural Domain area, namely the CIDOC CRM, has been assumed as the conceptual backbone of AO, providing a unified and coherent linguistic and axiomatic framework to the project. Subsequently, the CRM has been specialised, under a specially devised namespace to cater to the needs of the different aspects tackled by the ARIADNEplus project. The first of those specialisations is AO-Cat, the part of AO dealing with the representation of the resources in the ARIADNE Catalogue. The AO-Cat was developed during the first months of the project, and has been used to build the ARIADNE Catalogue. The second round of specialisations are the application profiles, which have been developed to support the integration of more specialised item-level data of the ARIADNE partners into the ARIADNE Content Cloud.

The ARIADNE Catalogue provides a collection-level representation of the resources shared by the partners of the project. The distinction between collection level and item level may seem like an obvious one, but can be applied in many ways, according to how we define what we consider to be items. This will in turn depend on the specific research context and research question. For example, at the level of landscape research, each archaeological site may be considered to be an item of observation, and the collection-level record refers to the database of national sites and monuments, whereas for an artefact-based study, the individual objects may be the items of interest, and the collection-level record now refers to the database of artefacts, potentially from across several sites.

In the first phase of ARIADNE (2012-16), the ARIADNE project produced a catalogue that already included summary metadata records for archaeological sites and monuments at item level, and these were searchable via the ARIADNE portal. This approach has been retained in ARIADNEplus, and has been labelled sub-task 4.4.0. In the first phase of ARIADNE, i.e. during the ARIADNE project, we also undertook some experiments in more granular item-level integration, most notably investigating interoperability between several databases of coins held by different partners (Felicetti et al 2015). In ARIADNEplus such developments are now the domain of the application profile.

However, it is worth noting that AO-Cat is itself an application profile for what we might regard as higher level archaeological observations. It captures the basic “What?”, “When?” and “Where?” information that powers our portal search interface, and provides an adequate representation for the discovery of resources relating to archaeological sites and monuments. It has also become apparent that it provides adequate core information for other sub-domains where “What?”, “When?” and “Where?” capture the core metadata and data, as in the case of archaeological artefacts (4.4.7) for example. In other cases, it can provide a collection level record for other classes of monument, such as buildings or underwater archaeological sites, although an application profile may be needed to deal with the specific research questions of the sub-domain. In these cases, the single AO-Cat record may provide the jumping off point and linkage from the discovery portal for an application profile implemented in one of the D4Science VREs. The extent to which it has been agreed that the AO-Cat is sufficient, or where it can be used as a collection-level pointer to item-level records will be considered as each sub-domain and application profile is discussed below.

The AO-Cat was introduced in detail in deliverable D4.1 and in deliverable D4.3 we took the opportunity to report on updates to the AO-Cat since Month 18. This information will not be repeated here.

After the updates reported in D4.3, the AO-Cat ontology has not changed, supporting in an adequate manner the aggregation process of the project with its expressive power. In other words, the addition of a large collection of resources to the Catalogue has not required any change to the ontology, in spite of the fact that the last additions have come from a larger number of partners than those contributing to the early phases. This indicates that the ontology has reached a mature level of stability and is therefore ready for wider usage outside the boundaries of the ARIADNEplus project. Indeed, within the UK the AO-Cat has been adopted by Unpath'd Waters, a major project to characterise and aggregate digital data concerning the rich maritime heritage of the UK.² This is actually no surprise, since AO-Cat is based on a well-known and largely employed standard, the CIDOC CRM, which has itself reached a solid level of stability. The work of the two ARIADNE Projects has mostly consisted in the application of the CIDOC CRM to the archaeological domain, and we may consider this application to be successfully completed.

As will be argued in Section 6, the AO-Cat turns out to be adequate also for the representation requirements of the archaeological domains. In fact the model provides suitable classes for high-profile description of artefacts and other archaeological objects (*AO-Object*), places (*AO-Spatial-Region*) and events (*AO-Event*), and thus, supplies the abstraction of archaeological entities at a higher conceptual level, which is of paramount importance for interoperability and integration. The use of AO-Cat in an archaeological perspective becomes even more effective when employed in combination with entities of the other ARIADNE ontologies. Indeed, it is possible to instantiate at the same time classes of AO-Cat and of the other models of the ARIADNE Ontology in order to encode single multi-faceted archaeological entities and to provide structured descriptions of them at different levels of detail.

² <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/data-catalogue-launched/>

4 Application profiles and other compatible models

Application Profiles are particular ontological models whose purpose is to describe the information relating to a specific research domain in a coherent and complete way. The philosophy behind the definition of an Application Profile is that of reusing the elements of existing ontologies and models for the description of similar entities in the new research context, limiting the development of new elements only for the description of peculiar and typical aspects of the specific discipline. In ARIADNEplus, for instance, we selected classes of the CIDOC CRM ontology and from the Dublin Core standard to define an application profile for the description of scientific data at the item level. The AO-Cat model itself is an application profile defined for the specific purpose of creating the new ARIADNE catalogue, and is entirely modelled as an extension of the CIDOC CRM.

The reuse of already existing, well-consolidated and widely used conceptual elements for the construction of the new schema, ensures the solidity of the new model and confers extensive compatibility. This approach also provides the opportunity to create ‘simplified’ classes that correspond (i.e. are mapped) to existing classes to customise the model as much as possible. In this way, scholars are able to focus on the specific problems of their discipline and just define the new entities necessary for their research domain in an existing well-structured and integrated ontological context.

In ARIADNEplus, the work of creating application profiles has been delegated to 14 special interest groups, each aligned with the 13 initial sub-tasks of T4.4, with the addition of a burial special interest group in response to interest from the consortium. Each special interest group was convened by a sub-task leader drawn from the archaeological partners, supported by UoY-ADS and PIN. The groups were charged with surveying, collecting, creating and managing multilingual domain thesauri and vocabularies, as well as developing application profiles, designing semantic extensions and creating services and tools for the specific purposes of their domains.

The activities and the discussions of the working groups have evidenced that in many cases the AO-Cat is sufficient, without further modification and enhancement, to cover the needs of their sub-domains, even for the item-level data aggregation. In other cases, they worked to define extensions to the AO-Cat itself. The different strategies used for the development of the ARIADNEplus application profiles are described in detail in the next paragraphs.

Several external models and ontologies, used during the work of definition of the various ARIADNEplus application profiles and mostly belonging to the CIDOC CRM family of ontologies, are mentioned throughout the document. Table 1, below, provides a reference to all the cited ontological models and the prefixes used to identify their classes and properties.

Model / Ontology	Prefixes (Classes / Properties)	Description
CIDOC CRM	E / P	A formal ontology for Cultural Heritage information
CRMarchaeo	A / AP	Extension to support the archaeological excavation process
CRMba	B / BP	Extension to support buildings archaeology documentation
CRMdig	D / L	Model for provenance metadata
CRMinf	I / J	Extension of CIDOC CRM to support argumentation.
CRMpe	PE / PP	The PARTHENOS Entities model
CRMsci	S / O	The scientific observation model

Table 1: External ontological models used for the definition of the ARIADNEplus application profiles.

The following sections present the details of the work of defining application profiles for each ARIADNEplus research subdomain.

4.1 Palaeo-anthropology

The activities of task 4.4.1 were aimed at encoding and integrating Palaeo-anthropology information after identifying the particularities of the data produced by this research domain. A relevant contribution to this activity was provided by CENIEH, who provided information related to Comparative Anatomy, Osteological collection, Rocks collection (Lithotec), Modern Human Teeth and Sediment data. The contribution of the project "The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans" (ROCEEH) of the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities was also noteworthy and substantial. Their data was contributed to ARIADNEplus by researchers from University of Tübingen, actively working on ROCEEH. This project has gathered ~8.000 archaeological assemblages from ~1700 localities in Africa/Eurasia and stored it in the ROAD Database.³ The data comprise predominantly early human cultural and biological artefacts, as well as environmental data, which have been extracted from scientific publications and excavation data (e.g. UNESCO Swabian Jura).

Despite these institutions using different data schemas and vocabularies, and organising the data according to different criteria, resulting in as many perspectives in which the data of a domain is managed, the aggregation and integration of this complex information in ARIADNEplus has been accomplished in a satisfactory way. The AO-Cat has also proved sufficient to describe peculiar palaeoanthropological concepts such as the assemblage and the stratified deposit of biological objects and thanks to its use it has been possible to integrate information about more than 1800 sites and 10,000 assemblages of the Africa Database (ROAD), and a collection of information about archaeo-paleontological excavation sites provided by CENIEH. The challenges of mapping the ROAD database

³ https://www.roceeh.uni-tuebingen.de/roadweb/smarty_road_simple_search.php

schema to the AO-Cat were described by the ROCEEH team in a paper presented to the CHNT2023 conference in Vienna, and will be published in a special issue of the peer-reviewed Open Access e-journal *Internet Archaeology* to be published in 2023 (Kandel et al forthcoming).

4.2 Bio-archaeology and Ancient DNA

Ancient DNA (aDNA) is a highly multidisciplinary field that can be viewed as the intersection of bioarchaeology & archaeogenetics, paleoanthropology & human evolution, biodiversity & population genetics and anthropometry & forensics science. As such, it involves experts from biology, geology, chemistry, to name just a few and requires modelling, analytical technologies, computational services and data science, generating large amounts of data even before the samples reach the laboratory.

aDNA investigates humans as individuals, groups or societies and their lives in the past as well as ancient animal and plant populations.

Indicative areas of aDNA studies include:

- genetic structure of ancient populations – like origins, identities and ancestry;
- construction of social organisation with indications of population diversity;
- infectious diseases & health status (for example pathogens);
- expansions and extinctions of animals, domestication;
- cultural routines, nutrition, migration (mobility patterns);
- sex, gender issues.

The development of high-throughput sequencing (HTS), as well as advances in the recovery of aDNA, have revolutionised aDNA analysis. Protocols and methods for the analysis of precious and unique archaeological biological findings are continuously being improved and expanding, aiming to extract the maximum information such specimens have to offer. Analysis of ancient DNA involves several steps, starting from estimating the suitability of a specific sample, sample preparation, documentation, different steps of analysis, data generation, exploitation of the results etc. Ancient DNA analysis protocols are precise scientific investigation methods that allow for inferring, approximating or excluding causes from measured or observed effects.

An aDNA project always starts with the excavation and burial data of the human or faunal remains and ends with the interpretation of the aDNA data. Selection and evaluation of the samples is a crucial initial step. Challenges such as degradation and contamination of samples are commonplace and the context of biological material is very important to be able to get meaningful research results. So, it is crucial for an aDNA project to have access to all relevant contextual information and the respective documentation.

There are three basic types of data that can provide a unique understanding of the genetic data that derives from them (see Figure 1):

- burial data and disposal of the dead is one of the most common classes of archaeological data, in both prehistoric and historic contexts.

- excavation data and excavation activities data. In both cases there are more or less standardised documentation practices and recording methodologies.
- museum data about the collection, preservation, storage, conservation, of the skeletal material which occurs in various types of records but most of the time is fragmented, incomplete or even unreliable.

Figure 1: Large amounts of data generated before the sample reaches the lab for aDNA analysis

Subtask 4.4.2 analysed both the contextual information and the informal descriptions and formal metadata related to the scientific aDNA analysis workflow in order to produce a suitable application profile based on AO-Cat, CIDOC CRM and the family of its compatible models.

Modelling scientific workflows usually focuses on the digital data produced and ignores the large and complex experimental steps which are described only in the scientists' lab-books. In our approach, we analysed all steps of an aDNA project, starting from sampling, storage, DNA extraction, genomic library construction, sequencing, bioinformatics analyses, interpretation of the results and conclusions up to the publication of results. Furthermore, we aligned the aDNA application profile with CRMhs, the heritage science model which is suitable for modelling scientific analyses (e.g. C14 or XRF) carried out on biological objects and cultural artefacts. Our goal is to specify an adequate form and extent of metadata that allows for effective control of provenance ensuring quality, validity, and FAIRness of data.

The aDNA application profile describes the aDNA wet lab services and links the sample data with contextual information. It is based on CIDOC CRM and the family of its compatible models and is aligned with CRMhs and the Mortuary application profile:

- CIDOC CRM – The base model, version 6.2.1
- CRMsci – Scientific observation model, version 1.2.2

- CRMdig – Model for provenance metadata, version 3.2
- CRMarchaeo – Excavation model, version 1.4.1
- CRMpe – Model for Research Infrastructure management, the PARTHENOS Entity Model version 3.1.2
- CRMhs – Heritage Science model, version 1.0
- Mortuary AP, version 1.2

The modelling details of the aDNA application profile have been presented in detail in deliverable D4.2 Initial report on ontology implementation.

Moreover Subtask 4.4.2 produced a glossary specific to the aDNA field [Psonis, Tabakaki and Vassou 2022].

The aDNA application profile was extensively discussed in the second Virtual Research Environments (VRE) Workshop, May 6, 2021⁴ which featured two relatively new areas of archaeology – Ancient DNA and Environmental Data & Research.

Figure 2: aDNA application profile and CRMhs alignment.

⁴ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/the-2nd-vre-workshop-ancient-dna-and-environmental-data-and-research/>

Figure 3: aDNA application profile and CRMhs alignment examples.

4.3 Environmental Archaeology

The aim of sub-task 4.4.3 was mainly to investigate suitable solutions for linking data of the SEAD project, a comprehensive international initiative aimed at the construction of scientific research infrastructures for both Sweden and internationally. SEAD provides a large amount of environmental and archaeological data, and a system that allows scholars to study the interactions of past environments, climates and human impact, and foster research on cultural heritage, species and landscape conservation. The SEAD database, hosted by Umea University (which is also leading this sub-task), includes information about a range of environmental data, including insects, pollen, seeds, as well as scientific dating information⁵.

The activities of this task started from an initial survey which highlighted the absence of comparable information in the datasets of other ARIADNEplus partners. The survey also evidenced the complexity of implementing an item-level integration for a domain such as that of environmental archaeology in which the basic data consists mostly of individual seeds, insects and pollen. The survey also revealed the existence, in this domain, of a huge variety of complex vocabularies, often overlapping with each other.

⁵ The SEAD Database is accessible at <https://www.sead.se>.

From an implementation point of view, the relational structure of the SEAD database has allowed a perfect mapping of its content to AO-Cat, especially as regards the description of the sites and their contexts. The AO-Cat model proved adequate and no additional ontology or application profile was therefore necessary for the integration of this information at the collection level. Additionally, the CRMhs model (see sections 4.4 and 4.5) has been tested for the encoding of the detailed scientific aspects of this data. The results were very fruitful and highlighted the possibility of using this application profile, should it become desirable to implement a deeper integration at item-level, although it was agreed that there was little to be gained by attempting to duplicate the functionality of SEAD.

The combined use of AO-Cat, CRMsci and CRMarchaeo allows for a detailed description of activities on sites and archaeological environments, and makes it also possible to create links between this research domain and other closely related ones, such as natural and geological sciences. The variety of terminological resources available in this domain has been managed by mapping relevant concepts to AAT and reusing other similar vocabularies already AAT-mapped, such as those defined by ADS for describing closely related archaeological entities. The extensive use of vocabularies fosters the implementation of additional layers of standardisation on this data and makes it possible to use relevant terms for setting up interdisciplinary integrated scenarios.

4.4 Inorganic Materials Study (and)

4.5 Dating

The first version of CRMhs, the application profile for scientific data, was released during the first phase of the project and was extensively documented in Deliverable D4.2 (specifically in Chapters 4.4 and 4.5, in Chapter 5 and in the Appendix of that report). The model has been specifically designed for the encoding of information produced in the domain of Inorganic Materials Study (subtasks 4.4.4), Dating (subtask 4.4.5), and in general for all types of data deriving from Heritage Science research.

During the last phase of the ARIADNEplus project, the CRMhs application profile was further extended and equipped with new entities for the description of scientific research protocols and their application methodologies⁶. Each protocol, in fact, consists of a series of successive steps, each of which may be additionally expanded in (sub)steps. For all of these steps it is necessary to provide details about the right way of performing them so that the experiment is carried out in a correct way, including:

- The duration of the step
- The equipment to be used
- The substances, reagents and other elements to be used
- Specifications concerning the methodology used
- Details concerning element quantities, concentrations etc.
- The software to be used (e.g., the one that needs to be mounted on digital devices)
- The parameters, value tables, numeric information and other documentation necessary to perform the step or edit results.

⁶The documentation of the CRMhs application profile is available at <https://data.d4science.net/7RpU>.

Furthermore, each step is closely linked to the previous one, since it is necessary to always complete a certain step in order for the next one to take place. Specific classes and properties have been defined in CRMhs to document the order in which the steps should occur during the analysis phase and thus to define adequate step sequences, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Steps, sub-steps and sequences in CRMhs protocols definition.

Other specific properties are defined to describe the features required to perform the protocol as a whole or each step of it, such as its prescribed duration, the equipment and software needed to perform it, the methodologies to be used, and so on.

During the last period, a flexible user-friendly interface, called THESPIAN-MASK⁷, has also been developed by INFN for the cataloguing and storage of scientific data. THESPIAN-MASK is able to encode scientific information in CRMhs and AO-Cat format, provides all the necessary facilities to make the data entry process fast and efficient (e.g., autocomplete, reuse of previously inserted information, date pickers and so on). THESPIAN-MASK is also equipped with advanced features for Linked Open Data automatic acquisition and incorporation and is able to query remote thesauri and gazetteer (such as Getty AAT and PeriodO) for the rapid inclusion of conceptual and spatial information (see Figure 5).

⁷ The tool is accessible at <https://ch.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/metadatamask/>.

Figure 5: THESPIAN-MASK interfaces for the encoding of scientific data in CRMhs and AO-Cat format.

Overall, CRMhs is the result of the activities of the scientific data working group specifically set up for the definition of this model and composed by partners from INFN, Cyl, HNM, PIN, OEAW and LNEC and has been designed to take advantage of the most important international standards and vocabularies for a perfect integration of scientific data. The model is also perfectly compatible with AO-Cat and with the whole ecosystem of the CIDOC CRM, in particular with CRMsci, the CIDOC CRM extension developed for the semantic description of scientific observations.

An additional task aimed at the harmonisation of CRMhs with the model developed for Bio-archaeology and ancient DNA (see Section 4.2) was carried out during the second half of the project in order to define a complete framework for the description of all the data related to scientific activities that ARIADNEplus aims to integrate. The synergy between the two application profiles allows the encoding of very detailed scientific information, concerning for instance analyses, the instrumentation used, the various activities of extraction and preparation of samples and all the other operations typical of the targeted research domains by using a combination of the most suitable entities of both the models. A further level of compatibility within ARIADNEplus is established by the inclusion of CRMhs as part of the general framework of the ARIADNE Ontology.

4.6 Field Survey

Sub-task 4.4.6 focussed its work on survey data derived from field-walking, an archaeological activity having some peculiarities from a conceptual point of view, but also presenting many similarities with the procedures of the metal detector surveys (4.4.7) and of remote sensing activities (4.4.8).

Archaeological field surveys, in fact, are coordinated sets of survey activities performed on a single, discrete area of a broader topographical context of investigation, during a single continuous time period and according to a specific protocol, aimed at the collection of archaeologically relevant observations, objects or archaeological samples. The investigated areas are defined with artificially or physically defined boundaries by imposing geographical grids independent of the landscape arrangements, or by making use of natural boundaries. If allowed by the legal framework of the relevant country, collection of objects may take place by removing material from the surface. Such material samples are considered indicative of aspects of the identified material surface and sites from which they are taken, providing information regarding their dating and past use.

During the first part of ARIADNEplus, a general overview of field walking surveys taking place in the Mediterranean zone was provided by Fasti Online Survey, a service managed by AIAC. The analysis of Fasti Online Survey, containing basic metadata on circa 120 survey projects in the Italian peninsula, revealed that many of these projects have only published their datasets partially (e.g. providing site gazetteers), or not at all. Few of them have published their data fully, and even fewer have supplied a digital data archive to a repository. Currently archived and accessible survey datasets in ARIADNEplus partners DANS and UoY-ADS only form a small minority, and although these are Findable, Accessible and largely Interoperable, they do not comply with the Re-usability criterion, which requires higher standards of documentation.

The generally systematic character of archaeological field surveying, combined with the above considerations, led to the conclusion that the models of the ARIADNE and CIDOC CRM ecosystems look already suitable to describe the information of this domain for populating the ARIADNE data space with suitable information, when they will become available. A thorough examination at the conceptual level of the main entities of this discipline has proved that AO-Cat and CIDOC CRM already provide adequate entities to describe survey investigations (*AO_Event*, *E7 Activity*), the explored survey areas and surfaces (*S20 Rigid Physical Feature*), the events of discovery and the collection of samples and archaeological materials (*S2 Sample Taking*, *S19 Encounter Event*), and the collected objects (*AO-Object*, *E18 Physical Object*) and samples (*S13 Sample*) themselves. By defining subclasses of these classes survey data may be mapped in more detail.

ARIADNEplus partner and sub-task leader RUG published an embryonic proposal for a possible future extension in the AIAC FASTI online journal (de Haas and van Leusen 2020). Working with ARIADNE Associate partner Takin Solutions, they then developed a formal proposal for a CIDOC CRM extension which was presented to the CIDOC CRM SIG on 14 October 2022. They propose several new CRM classes and properties to serve archaeological field survey:

- U1: Archaeological Survey, subclass of E7 Activity
- U2: Survey Collection Activity, subclass of S19 Encounter Event and S2 Sample Taking
- U3: Survey Process Unit, subclass of S19 Encounter Event
- U4: Survey Surface Unit, subclass of S20 Rigid Physical Feature
- U5: Digitization Process Unit, subclass of D2 Digitization Process and S19 Encounter Event
- U6: Material Sample, subclass of S13 Sample and E18 Physical Object

Figure 6: U3 Survey Process Unit and related classes

In addition, in order to cover the most frequently used ‘types’ in field survey data processing, they have suggested some further additional classes under the Superclass E55 Type, with particular relevance to pottery found during field survey:

- U7: Fabric
- U8: Function
- U9: Ware
- U10: Shape
- U11: Vessel Part

Finally, they have proposed one new property: UP1 has observation affecting parameter (is observation affecting parameter for). This property describes the effects of an E55 Type on an S4 Observation. It describes how different parameters (such as vegetation cover, tillage regime, sunlight, etc) affect the quality of different kinds of observations made during an instance of U3 Survey Process Unit. The proposal contains interesting constructs which could be integrated within CRMarchaeo and could provide a step towards a model to integrate all kinds of archaeological finds.

Figure 7: property up1

The SEMAFORA project, funded by the NWO Open Science Fund, and running from March 2022 to March 2023, is currently building and testing a tool to map survey datasets to the CRM,⁸

4.7 Archaeological finds made by general public

This task examined the integration of finds recorded by members of the public (mainly metal detector finds). This was achieved through facilitating the harvest of data from several of the different national user driven recording schemes, many of which already cooperate under the umbrella of the European Public Finds Recording Network (EPFRN). The largest dataset came from the British Museum’s Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS) for England and Wales, comprising over 470,000 artefacts and a similar number of coins. In addition we aggregated 48884 records from the Portable Antiquities of the Netherlands (PAN), 8687 from the Danish scheme (DIME), and 3025 from FindSampo, the Finnish scheme. These schemes all aim at the inclusion of archaeological objects found by members of the public in the archaeological record and at making them publicly accessible for researchers and the general public alike.⁹ It should be noted that this kind of activity is not allowed in some countries, including France and Italy where any kind of organised archaeological survey – including amateur activity – is subject to permission by governmental archaeological offices, and is usually granted only to professionals. In these cases, casual discovery of archaeological finds must generally be immediately reported to the authority and the objects found, if collected, must be delivered to them. Therefore, few data sets were available for such countries that include most Southern European

⁸ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/203001119>

⁹ <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/public-finds-in-the-ariadneplus-data-infrastructure/>

states, although we were able to add a small number of finds records from a new scheme in the Czech Republic, managed by AIS CR. Finally, the RGK contributed their considerable database of Roman coins to this activity, and CYi provided metadata for a smaller collection of coins held in the National Museum of Cyprus.

In much of Northern Europe and Scandinavia, the development over the past decades of databases for finds made by members of the public is closely linked with more general tendencies towards inclusive approaches in heritage management and the paradigm of digital humanities. Hence, task 4.4.7 was closely linked to task 16.5 – ARIADNEplus for public/community archaeology, which aimed to investigate trajectories of public inclusion and participation and at demonstrating the added value of ARIADNEplus for non-professional archaeologists, through incorporation of principles of citizen science and crowd-sourcing.

The working group, led by AU, concluded that the AO-Cat was largely sufficient to adopt as the ontology for 4.4.7, particularly after the addition of images as one of the optional properties. Artefact research largely depends upon the What, When, and Where criteria which are well supported by AO-Cat, although the other change made was to allow the blurring of spatial coordinates, and their representation within bounding boxes, to protect find locations. The data contributing to Task 4.4.7 can easily be filtered by application of the ARIADNE_subjects “Artefact” and “Coin”.

The other conclusion of Task 4.4.7 was that more fine-grained vocabularies needed to be developed to achieve interoperability at a fine level for finds classification, and they proposed that could be achieved via extensions to the Getty AAT. There is a need for investment in this area. It also became clear that it is important that partners map their finds classifications to the AAT in a consistent fashion to allow effective cross-search.

4.8 Remote Sensing

Archaeological remote and near-surface sensing data (ARNSS) data is produced through the application of a range of techniques e.g., colour photography, LiDAR, multispectral imaging, ground-penetrating radar, and magnetic gradiometry, using satellite, aerial, and terrestrial platforms, to assess the potential preservation of, detect the presence of and characterising the properties of subsurface or surface archaeological remains. These data have significant potential for reuse in the context of integrated land management, sustainable land management, and the promotion of landscape heritage. Their reuse potential beyond archaeology is high because they include information on the geophysical, geochemical and geotechnical character of buried soils, the inclusion of anthropogenic materials in buried soils, modifications of the morphology of the land’s surface, and the impacts of modifications to soils and surface morphology on plant communities.

Remote sensing data is a special case within scientific and geospatial data (see 4.10 which addresses geospatial and GIS data). In particular, task 4.8 addressed the discoverability of archaeological data, which are available in a standardised form and easy to integrate with other spatial data for any use-case even outside archaeology. It also made specific recommendations for future data providers

mapping their data to ARIADNEplus, mainly by distinguishing data (fieldwork archives) from reports, identifying key metadata elements beyond those included in AO-Cat entries, and selecting AAT subject mappings to maximise findability outside archaeology and heritage management.

In particular, fieldwork archives are datasets that contain what is commonly referred to as ‘raw’, calibrated/cleaned or processed data. In these datasets, measured values or values produced through a calculation or analysis of the measured values are represented. These data can be geolocated. Examples of fieldwork archive items include orthorectified vertical aerial photographs, georeferenced oblique aerial photographs, georeferenced GPR time slices, and georeferenced sky view factor visualisations of lidar-derived terrain models.

Fieldwork reports are instead datasets that contain the products of archaeological interpretations of ARNSS data. Examples of fieldwork report items include written reports containing illustrations and commentary, non-geolocated images, and georeferenced or non-georeferenced vector data (e.g. points, polylines, polygons with associated attributes) representing the archaeological interpretations of anomalies in ARNSS data.

Both fieldwork archives and fieldwork reports have good potential for reuse in archaeological and cultural heritage management applications. For this reason, in ARIADNEplus the application profile for remote sensing has been implemented through a process of reuse of the entities of existing ontology deemed relevant to maximise reusability and interoperability.

The set of minimal metadata necessary to make both the fieldwork archives and the reports interoperable and reusable have been encoded by means of AO-Cat. Any ARNSS dataset is considered to be an AO_Data_Resource. When supplying ARNSS information, core metadata elements such as author, location, dataset description, and publisher are supplied by means of the relevant entities of the AO_Cat schema. Additional and specific information, such as instrumentation, visualisation and calibration, useful for performing deep data analysis, scientific observations and interpretation, has been encoded by means of CIDOC CRM and its extension, including CRMsci and CRMhs, the Heritage Science application profile developed by ARIADNEplus (see 4.4).

Figures 8 and 9 illustrate the various workflows for properly structuring remote sensing information according to the defined application profile. A detailed description of all mappings, together with the indications on the AAT subjects recommended to maximise data standardisation, is available in the “Recommendations and Application Profile Proposal for archaeological remote and near-surface sensing data in ARIADNEplus” internal report¹⁰.

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6373050>.

Figure 8: Core components and workflow of the remote sensing application profile (no calibration).

Figure 9: Core components and workflow of the remote sensing application profile (with calibration).

4.9 Standing Structures

From March-May 2019, the sub-task leader, LNEC, undertook a survey of which partners held data concerning standing structures information. During this it became clear that most data was just held at collection level, where the AO-Cat as applied to sites and monuments was adequate for data aggregation. Some differences have been identified relating to specific concepts and semantics (especially related with events and activities), but globally the model already developed seems to be suitable. The challenges of mapping the CHNT database schema to the AO-Cat have been investigated by the team at LNEC and will be published in a paper in the ARIADNE special issue of the peer-reviewed Open Access e-journal *Internet Archaeology* to be published in 2023 (Correia and Santos Silva, forthcoming).

There are some examples of information about buildings and physical infrastructures which might be suitable for item level integration. The representation of the physical and functional characteristics of standing structure components, integrating their relations through space and time, is essential for operating and maintaining these assets. International standards on frameworks and classes should be considered for the model conceptualization at the item level. LNEC identified the relevant technical terms and periods for mapping to Getty AAT and Period0, contributing to the thesauri and vocabularies for the Standing Structures domain for which the existing CIDOC CRMba [Ronzino et al, 2022] extension is adequate.

CRMba, in fact, allows the subdivision of a building into its functional and structural components and the definition of connections among them. CRMba is also able to describe the different morphological and functional components of a building, being built upon the concept of “function”, either comprising the entire building and its specific parts. The model provides the *B1 Built Work* class, representing freestanding buildings, components, and complexes of buildings serving a practical purpose. Instances of B1 refer to built works composed of parts performing distinct functions within the building. B1 in turn has a *B2 Morphological Building Section* subclass to describe morphological aspects of the sections of a building. B1 and B2 are linked through the *BP1 has section* property, illustrating the relation existing between the building and its parts. Instances of B2 are functional elements of the whole building, e.g. walls, roof, foundations, rooms, etc., and are composed in turn of parts that are homogeneously filled with matter (*B3 Filled Morphological Building Section*), and of empty spaces (*B4 Empty Morphological Building Section*) deriving from an intentional disposition in the space of the filled parts, such as the opening of a window in a wall, a doorway, an intercolumniation and so on.

An important class from the ARIADNEplus perspective is the *B5 Stratigraphic Building Unit*, defined as subclass of the *A2 Stratigraphic Volume Unit* of CRMarchaeo and intended to identify the minimal construction unit of a built structure and any of the discontinuities of matter visible on a wall surface, witnessing human intervention. B5 is a volumetric entity confined by an interface represented by the CRMarchaeo *A3 Stratigraphic Interface* class. The CRMarchaeo *AP12 is confined by* property is used to link B5 and A3 in order to identify the different stratigraphic building units and, by linking temporal and other available information to them, to represent the evolution of the building, supporting its dating process. The essential entities of the CRMba model are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: The CRMba main classes and properties and their integration with CIDOC CRM and CRMarchaeo.

4.10 Spatio-temporal data

Most archaeological material has spatial properties and therefore collecting spatial data is a natural component of archaeological data processing. Subtask 4.4.10 was in charge of analysing the form in which spatial data is stored by the individual partners and how it can be integrated into the ARIADNE infrastructure at the item level. It was clear from the outset that subtask 4.4.10 overlaps in its focus with other subtasks within T4.4, as spatial information is an integral part of many different dataset types. In order to define realistic integration scenarios and to consider the need and development of a specific Application Profile, subtask 4.4.10 analysed the nature of the spatial data available in the datasets of the various partners involved in the project and the various solutions for its use and integration.

To this end, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to the ARIADNEplus partners, from which it became apparent that there are several national standards for data description in place. Some partners planned to make their datasets compliant with CIDOC CRM, while other data stayed non-standardized. Geospatial features representations in GIS datasets are usually variable, without any methodological specification, with some notable exceptions represented by partners having a transparent strategy of geodata classification and representation¹¹.

¹¹ The results of this and other surveys intended to identify geographic information already present in ARIADNEplus partners' datasets and services available and usable in the ARIADNEplus framework are available in the "An analysis of spatial data and how it can be integrated into the AO-CAT" ARIADNEplus internal report at https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/T4_4_10_Final_Report_public_v1.pdf.

Temporal (chronological) attributes often appear in the data, however on different levels. Item-level temporal data were usually present in all datasets stored by partners, but only a few datasets are described according to a shared standard. In other datasets, temporal data were included according to the decision of the data provider, and their automatic collection or harmonisation is currently impossible. Only a few partners were able to provide standardised temporal data on the collection level.

There are plenty of formats used by partners for geospatial data storage (SHP, DWG, DWF, GeoTIFF, GeoJSON, TIN, GRID, KML). ESRI shapefiles, GML and PostGIS databases seem to be prominent options chosen for data handling as well as for long-term preservation. Some partners were ready to publish (or published already) their geodata as web services (WMS/WFS) using GIS servers. All the datasets were described by metadata, which usually follows institutional national or international standards. The will to include geospatial data on the item level was expressed by a few partners while all the others were able to provide their data on the collection level only.

As a result, a high level of heterogeneity limiting the possibilities of integration of a wide range of existing GIS data were identified, and thus, the difficulty to find a common ground for harmonisation of specific items in geospatial databases provided by different partners. Harmonisation of GIS datasets would need direct and time-consuming intervention into the datasets to add shared metadata for each item. It might be even a complicated step in the case of repositories where licence rights and authorship of the datasets are kept by external providers.

Therefore it was decided to change the strategy for spatial data integration and to pursue the possibility of “passive” integration, using the geospatial services (WMS, WFS, WCS) provided by ARIADNEplus partners, and using existing or newly established GIS servers. This way of data sharing corresponds with collection-level integration, is flexible and may be continuously enhanced for future data that should become available. Many of the existing geospatial services are relevant for the field of archaeology; some are provided by the ARIADNEplus partners with existing or newly established GIS servers, others are available for specific countries and managed by non-archaeological stakeholders.

Geospatial services can be considered equivalent to standard APIs developed for geospatial data, which are made available throughout the Internet and easily readable by most of the GIS software or webGIS libraries. To be accessible and findable, geospatial services need to be described according to the AO-Cat ontology and mapped to the ARIADNEplus data model. After evaluation of available services, it is possible to directly integrate them into the ARIADNE Portal for data visualisation (WMS) and (possibly) for querying (WFS, WCS) as implemented in the ARIADNEplus technical WPs.

Five types of entities relevant for description and integration were defined, namely: geospatial service, geospatial layer, feature class, coverage, and service provider:

Geospatial service represents an instance `AO_Data_Resource`, which is structured according to relevant international standards and provided as an online service. It is described by metadata available upon request and may be queried for results. Depending on the service type and the specific request, a response of the query can be a geocoded image, set of geospatial records or structured metadata describing archaeological situations and/or their context. To query a service, it is needed to

know its location defined as URL (which serves as the base address for HTTP requests used to get the data or metadata), version and type. Type of service is information important both for further implementation into the ARIADNE Portal GIS environment and for description in the AO_Cat. Different types of services offer different solutions for viewing and querying, therefore, they should be linked to a fixed vocabulary of service types. Required information on the service can be easily described using standard properties in the AO_Cat (has_type, has_description and has_landing_page).

Geospatial layers and **feature classes** are specific outputs provided by geospatial services (WMS, respectively WFS) with uniform content, style and format. A layer may be composed of sublayers, a feature class is composed of individual features. Both entities correspond to the AO_Collection. A layer or feature class usually provides an individual dataset on a specific topic. It can be described by AO_Spatial_Region_BBox, AO_Temporal_Region and also by the attributes of its content (types of described objects etc.). For a better user experience and if appropriate technical prerequisites are met, it should be possible for a layer or feature class to be visualised in the ARIADNE Portal GIS environment upon user request.

Coverages are raster datasets provided by WCS services corresponding to the AO_Individual_Data_Resource entity. A raster dataset usually provides continuous and uniform geospatial data (grid) on selected topics in machine-readable and processable formats. Same way as layers or feature classes, it can be described by AO_Spatial_Region_BBox, AO_Temporal_Region or content attributes and can be visualised in the ARIADNE Portal webGIS.

A **service provider** is a standard AO_Cat entity classified as AO_Agent and interconnected with geospatial service by has_publisher property. It represents the institutions and persons responsible for the service provisioning and for the dataset it offers. The detail of the provider description should be like the description of any other data providers represented in the ARIADNE Portal.

The suggested solution for geospatial data builds on existing standards of data exchange proven by international and interdisciplinary practice. Analysis shows that the geospatial data application profile needs no specific amendments to the AO_Cat standard and that the data integration and possible re-use are dependent on the upcoming development of ARIADNEplus services, especially the ARIADNE Portal.

4.11 Maritime and underwater archaeology

In March 2019 DGPC undertook a survey of data sets and existing data standards but at that stage there were few other partners with relevant data. Work resumed on the sub-task in November 2021 by UoY-ADS, who had joined a major UK Towards A National Collection programme initiative, entitled Unpath'd Waters.¹² The aim of this project is to bring together the vast array of data for the UK marine area. This extends over some 867,400 km², equivalent to 3.5 times the terrestrial land surface. The marine and maritime heritage of this vast area is exceptional and diverse. It encompasses submerged prehistoric landscapes, inundated monuments and settlements, wrecks and aircraft losses, maritime

¹² <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/>

industrial and military complexes, coastal and intertidal archaeology, seaside resorts, ports and dockyards.

UoY-ADS undertook an audit of all the maritime and marine heritage data held by the UK nations. It then undertook a mapping exercise and consultation to assess how far the AO-Cat could be adapted for this maritime data. The conclusion was that the data was actually a good fit, and that the AO-Cat ontology would address the research questions posed by the consortium.¹³ The only addition required was to add a third dimension to spatial recording, as Depth is important when recording the marine environment. ADS therefore created a slightly modified application profile of the AO-Cat, the UO-Cat, and has begun to map all the UK datasets against it, loading them to the ARIADNE knowledge base, using the ARIADNE_Subject 'Maritime'. This work will continue in 2023, under the auspices of Unpath'd Waters. It was also found that there was a good correspondence between the UO-Cat and the metadata schema followed by MEDIN, the Marine Environment Data Information Network.¹⁴

We have therefore concluded that the majority of aspects of maritime archaeology are covered by AO-Cat and can be treated as sites and monuments data, so for the ARIADNE partners no further application profile for marine data was required.

4.12 Archaeological fieldwork

The aim of Sub-task 4.4.12 was the definition of an Application Profile for archaeological fieldwork activity. An *Archaeological Excavation Modelling Working Group*, composed by many ARIADNE and non-ARIADNE institutions as well, and coordinated by PP, was created within this task to investigate the potential of developing an ontology for excavation data, explore the current state of excavation data modelling and propose a roadmap for further activities. In fact, as part of the data aggregation activities within the ARIADNEplus project, several partners are working with excavation data, have individual or groups of excavation datasets or were working on excavation data modelling to approach the item level integration of their datasets within larger aggregation structures. Thus, the working group aimed to explore the degree to which existing elements of AO-Cat and the wider CIDOC CRM family of models would suffice to provide semantic descriptions that would allow the sub-collection or item-level integration of excavation dataset examples.

The activities of the working group evidenced the centrality of the excavation process as the most significant data generator of archaeological practice, requiring great attention in terms of its ontological significance and interfacing with sub-domain specific practices (like digital fieldwork documentation, laboratory studies and interpretive processes). Analytical work in the description of the excavation universe needs to be complemented by synthetic attempts that can foster a more stable and user-friendly ecosystem of methods and tools for all those researchers who want to structure their data in meaningful and interoperable ways. Towards this end the group has moved away from the need of a separate AP for excavation research and has instead tried to identify some

¹³ An assessment of the SeaLiT ontology extension to the CIDOC-CRM (Kritsotaki, Fafalios and Doerr 2022) was also conducted but this emphasised that its focus on maritime history made it unsuitable for tangible heritage, including shipwrecks.

¹⁴ <https://medin.org.uk/>.

key areas (models, questions, methods, workflow & tools and learning & training) where further work can provide all the necessary aspects for excavation datasets to be both FAIR and especially Re-usable.

An additional and quite important benefit of the group's activities was achieving to bring together what has largely been a fragmented community of scholars working in the same direction. Members of the group include researchers that apart from developing, try to implement archaeological excavation semantic modelling in existing datasets and examples. The interest group has therefore managed to exchange ideas and advance concrete lines of thought within a largely unstructured research environment.

In terms of the future of the group several options were discussed. It was felt that this initiative should continue as the survival of the group could help approach a wider archaeological community. The most realistic option after the conclusion of ARIADNEplus is to maintain this group as an informal "discussion" or "special interest" group, and probably in relation to similar initiatives like the Semantic Heritage Research Data (SHeRD)¹⁵. Communication channels with relevant CIDOC CRM SIG will also be sought, so as to provide feedback from our experiences in trying to implement the model and get also informed on new CIDOC CRM related resolutions. To stay active, the organisation of relevant sessions in subsequent conferences (like the CAA or CHNT) will be pursued, to bring together this community. For the foreseeable future, PP decided to continue to steer the initiative even after the end of the project.

The outcomes of the working group, including some general considerations regarding the fundamental requirements of the archaeological fieldwork domain, the identification of the relevant entities involved in its description and the classes and properties selected to implement the Application Profile, are presented in [Section 5](#) of this document.

4.13 Inscriptions

CRMtex, the CIDOC CRM extension for the description of textual entities, has proved to be the ideal tool for integrating this information. The development of CRMtex and its harmonisation with AO-Cat in the framework of the ARIADNEplus ontology continued throughout the duration of ARIADNEplus and led to the definition of a complete application profile to be used for the modelling of every aspect of the texts and their close relationship with the monuments and the archaeological and artistic objects on which they appear. The main features of CRMtex and its use in ARIADNEplus have been illustrated as a case study in section 7 of the deliverable D4.2¹⁶. This section presents the most recent updates of the model, the new classes and properties added in the last period, and the new harmonizations with AO-Cat.

The study of ancient texts falls within different disciplines, generally grown around the specific characteristics of each class of documents (e.g. papyrology for the study of papyri, epigraphy for inscriptions, palaeography for the study of ancient manuscripts, numismatics for coins). Nevertheless,

¹⁵ The SHeRD discussion group is active at https://twitter.com/sherd_athens. A series of online seminars by the SHeRD group is also available at the respective Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCVKjdvN5CUaerqmE9DbvIWw/about>.

¹⁶ The full documentation of the CRMtex model is available at <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmtex/>.

an interdisciplinary approach is essential, and the identification of common elements is paramount to confer uniformity and interoperability to all the disciplines in question and to exploit complementary skills from different approaches.

A common feature in ancient and handwritten documents that needs to be evidenced and addressed is the tight relationship between the text and its support. In comparison to modern printed or digital texts, in fact, handwritten texts are typically characterised by their uniqueness, being the result of manual work rather than mechanised processes as occurs since the invention of modern printing techniques. Such characteristics make the study and digitisation of this type of documentation particularly arduous, especially since the close relationship between the text and its support, forming a unique study object, requires careful investigation and analysis. It should be noted that in the ancient world many types of inscriptions were created through mechanised processes as well, such as the legends on coins, medals, stamps, and seals. Nevertheless, the uniqueness of the written text remains unchanged in these cases also, for the peculiar history and relevance of the object carrying the texts, which in most of the cases is a cultural object having significance also for other disciplines (e.g., numismatics, archaeology, etc.).

The CRMtex model distinguishes the two levels (i.e., the inscription and the carrier) by using the CIDOC CRM *E22 Man-Made Object* class to describe physical objects such as coins, vases and monuments bearing written texts, and by providing a specific *TX1 Written Text* class to model the texts themselves and all their peculiar features. The CIDOC CRM property *P56 is found on* is used to directly relate the text to its support. The separation between physical carrier and text and the use of the P56 property allow the coherent descriptions of scenarios in which the same object bears two or more texts, as in the case of the inscriptions shown on the obverse and reverse sides of a coin, and to assign different typologies and origin (i.e., production events) to them (see Figure 11). To establish full compatibility with AO-Cat, created instances of E22 and TX1 are automatically defined also as instances of the *AO-Object* class, by means of a double instantiation operation that allows the inheritance of all the related AO-Cat properties for the proper incorporation in the ARIADNEplus Catalogue. This technique represents one of the most used mechanisms for the construction of the ARIADNE Ontology.

Figure 11: CRMtex, CIDOC CRM and AO-Cat modelling of a Medieval coin bearing inscriptions on the obverse and reverse sides (from Cyprus Institute archives).

In addition to the tools for structural description of textual entities, CRMtex also provides classes and properties to represent the languages, scripts and alphabets used for their writing (*TX3 Writing System*), and to model the operations typically performed by scholars to investigate and study the texts. The new version of CRMtex, in fact, introduces new classes to model the operations of reading (*TX11 Reading*), deciphering and understanding (*TX5 Text Recognition*), translating and transcribing (*TX6 Transliteration*) the texts. These new entities are also perfectly integrated into the CIDOC CRM ecosystem and fully interoperable with AO-Cat, as shown in the example in Figure 12.

Figure 12: CRMtex, CIDOC CRM and AO-Cat modelling of the various investigation operations (i.e., reading, understanding, transliterating and translating) of an ancient Greek inscription from Cyprus, bearing an epigram of the ancient poet Myrto (Cyprus Institute archives).

For the investigation of specific portions of text and of the interconnections existing between a text and its parts, CRMtex also provides the *TX7 Written Text Segment* class, which allows the identification of specific textual components that scholars need to focus on for study purposes, as for instance, text segments, columns, sections and paragraphs, but also single words or letters. This provides the possibility to link specific production activities to each individual segment, or specific destruction events, as in the case of letters or words damaged or worn out due to natural deterioration or human interventions. Specifications about the conditions (E3) of each textual segment can be easily asserted and connected to it during the observation process, in order to model the specific observations and interpretations performed on each of them (see Figure 13).

A technical implementation of CRMtex is shown in Section 6.2 of deliverable D14.2, presenting the semantic search demonstrator, where the model is used to integrate numismatic and epigraphic data and query them at the item level.

Figure 13: CRMtex and CIDOC CRM modelling of text segments and the related conditions and events.

4.14 Burials

Mortuary archaeology consists of a series of research activities and analyses carried out either directly on mortuary evidence (archaeological evidence containing human remains or contexts that are interpreted to relate to the disposal of the dead), and/or on documentation and finds (human remains, objects, samples) from such contexts. Mortuary evidence provides information firstly about ways of disposal of the corpse, past funerary practices, other practices that involved human remains; secondly, mortuary data is used as a proxy for many aspects of past societies, such as identities, migration, social complexity, landscape and memory, beliefs, art and craft, technologies.

Important information for the interpretation of mortuary records comes from human osteology and other science-based analyses of human remains. Hence, mortuary archaeology is closely related to these fields and integrates their results for synthesis. Osteology informs about age-at-death, sex, stature, pathologies and other characteristics of skeletal remains. Recent major developments of science-based analyses include ancient DNA (e.g. family relationships, mobility) and stable isotopes (nutrition, origin), whilst radiocarbon dating has been around for longer.

Research questions and approaches to the analysis of mortuary data may vary due to historical developments, different scholarly traditions and fields, as well as differences in the archaeological record across archaeological periods and regions.

The working group led by OEAW, which also coordinated this task, performed a preliminary analysis of the ARIADNEplus partners' datasets/collections from the mortuary domain, concluding that data are usually generated at different stages of the workflow, involving the participation of different actors and the use of specific devices and software. All these elements are considered relevant in order to define adequate metadata for scientific datasets. Datasets are archived at the various stages of the workflow and made available to be re-examined by the experts who analyse them for new research questions and syntheses, leading to creation of new datasets. The stages at which datasets may be created typically include:

1. Datasets generated in the field with no or only limited post-excavation analysis, which often include information about other types of evidence too.
2. Datasets generated as results of analytical workflows based on fieldwork documentation (digital datasets, or, in previous times analogous documentation) and physical objects (human remains and objects).
3. Datasets that synthesise/aggregate mortuary data. They contain structured data that was extracted from datasets of above types (1, 2) and from publications (articles, books, grey literature). They may also be integrating other structured datasets (3) synthesising information.

Figures 14 and 15 provide a graphical representation of the research process and its resulting datasets.

Figure 14: Entities and relationships of activities in mortuary archaeology leading to datasets type 1 and 2.

Figure 15: Entities and relationships of activities leading to datasets type 3.

Datasets of above type 1, i.e. field data from the mortuary domain can be treated like a ‘Fieldwork archive’ with the addition of the “Burial” ARIADNEplus Subject to indicate the nature of their content. Since these types of datasets are only described at the collection level, the properties and classes of the AO-Cat are sufficient. Datasets of the type 2 would also fall under the category of ‘Fieldwork

archive’, but datasets of the type 3 fall under the ARIADNE subject ‘Site/Monument’. AO-Cat is also sufficient to describe the collection-level of these datasets. On the other hand, the item-level integration of burial data requires a specific application profile that was defined to fully describe the complexity of this information.

The resulting “Mortuary Data AP” is suitable for the description of the typical entities of a cemetery database, such as site (cemetery or other site types containing mortuary deposits); feature (different types of graves, ditches, pits and other features that contain mortuary deposits); mortuary deposit (the deposit of human remains and other finds, including containers and furniture); finds (human remains, artefacts, animal remains, samples). The AP was built using a combination of AO-Cat, the entities taken from the CIDOC CRM ecosystem, and the ARIADNEplus application profiles developed for other research domains (Aspöck et al 2022)

For instance, the CIDOC CRM *E13 Attribute Assignment* class was used to document that the attribution of types and the observations that were made are to a degree dependent on the methods that were used and on the views of the person who created/curated the database. The concepts of “burial site”/ “cemetery” were encoded through the CIDOC CRM *E27 Site* class, to describe its features in detail. The *A8 Stratigraphic Unit* class of the CRMarchaeo was used to model the individual features of a burial site/archaeological context, e.g., graves, but also pits, ditches, animal graves, coffins, and sometimes buildings. The CIDOC CRM *E22 Human-Made Object* and *E20 Biological Object* class were used for describing finds, e.g., grave goods and artefacts, and human and animal remains.

The “Mortuary Data AP” was developed for (and tested on) data coming from the ‘In Touch with the Dead’, a database holding information about early medieval cemeteries in the Low Countries,¹⁷ ARIADNE partner NIAM-BAS, and ARIADNE Associate partner THANADOS, an Austrian anthropological and archaeological database of cemeteries and graves.¹⁸ The beauty of the mapping of THANADOS to AO-Cat is that we were able to use ARIADNE resource types ‘Site/Monument’, ‘Burial’ and ‘Artefact’ to mirror the relational structure of the THANADOS database, allowing users to filter according to the level of granularity of interest to them. A complete description of the Mortuary AP and the way it has been used in the framework of ARIADNEplus is available in the “Types of burial data and proposal of a Mortuary Data Application Profile for ARIADNEplus (WP4.4.14)” internal report.¹⁹ A detailed description of the technical implementation of the Burials Application Profile within the ARIADNEplus infrastructure is also provided in deliverable Sections 4.5 and 6.3 of deliverable D14.2.

¹⁷ Haperen, M.C. van (Leiden University) (2017): In Touch with the Dead: Early Medieval Grave Reopenings in the Low Countries. DANS. <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-x6b-bvgj>.

¹⁸ THANADOS is an open source and open access online application that intends to present all so far published archaeological and anthropological data on early medieval cemeteries in nowadays Austria. See <https://thanados.net/>.

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7252485>.

5 Case study: Archaeological Fieldwork

Excavation fieldwork consists of a series of documentation activities and studies carried out in specific investigation areas as part of an excavation investigation strategy and archaeological (physical and architectural) objects or parts of them, to acquire information concerning their composition, origin, history in order to create an archaeological narrative that reconstructs the history of the site.

The datasets available in this domain are usually generated as results of articulated workflows of documentation processes and inferential thinking, involving the participation of different actors with various roles, the use of specific equipment, devices, software as well as argumentation activities. All these elements are considered relevant to define adequate metadata for intra-site archaeological datasets.

Excavation research is based on the precise identification of the remains of human activity in four dimensions (geometric space, i.e. X, Y, Z + chronology/time) at a specific place of investigation. Understanding the relationships of archaeological remains, both with each other and with the surrounding soil matrix, allows the reconstruction of the spatial arrangement of human behaviour and the recognition of its successive temporal phases, i.e. the history of the site.

From an archaeological perspective, an excavation research workflow in essence involves the contemporary break-up of the buried archaeological record into meaningful entities/units of observation that are structured and aggregated at subsequent research stages into several interrelated interpretive statements that together constitute a coherent and meaningful body of knowledge for the archaeological past in a given location.

5.1 General overview of the excavation workflow

A typical excavation research workflow can be outlined as follows, (classes and properties of the CIDOC CRM ecosystem are provided as well):

- An excavation (*A9 Archaeological Excavation*) takes place within a given location (e.g. site) or its spatial subdivision (e.g. a trench) (*E53 Place*) and proceeds through the decomposition of the soil matrix into designated units of excavation (e.g. single stratigraphic/arbitrary contexts) [*A1 Excavation Process Unit*] with substantial volume (e.g. strata removal) [*A8 Stratigraphic Unit*] or not (e.g. cleaning units).
- Within each unit of excavation, bulk and individual finds [*E18 Physical Thing*] are retrieved [*S19 Encounter Event*], while parts of each unit can be removed as samples of different types (e.g. flotation, C14) [*S13 Sample*]. During this process, architectural features (e.g. a wall, a pit) are located [*E26 Physical Feature*], stratigraphic interfaces are identified [*A3 Stratigraphic Interfaces*] and stratigraphic sections, recording the vertical stratification, are revealed [*S20 Rigid Physical Feature*].
- This process is documented in a set of documentation entities [*E73 Information Object* or *PE18 Datasets* or *D9 Data Object*] (e.g. journal records, sample forms, finds/feature catalogues, drawings, photographs, 3D models) that regardless of their analog or digital form are related to the systematic

recording of the above units of observation (e.g. units of excavation, finds, features, samples or sections).

- In subsequent or lateral stages some of these observation units (e.g. excavation units, samples) or retrieved objects (e.g. finds) are:

1. further compartmentalised into subsets (e.g. lithic finds) or constituent parts (e.g. flotation residue samples) [*E18 Physical object*] and subjected to separate processes of study or analyses through selection, sampling protocols, measuring activities using specific equipment (e.g. magnetic susceptibility) that end up in the creation of new datasets [*PE18 Datasets*].

2. aggregated into groups (e.g. pottery pieces into vessels, units of excavation into stratigraphic groups, features into architectural constructs, single drawings into composite drawings) [*A6 Group Declaration Event*] creating secondary (derived) datasets [*PE18 Datasets*].

- In this process, the archaeologist interacts with the documentation media and the datasets produced in addition to the physical evidence retrieved (e.g. finds or features) to transform the primary observations during fieldwork into processed archaeological information to be used in the site narrative [*I1 Argumentation*]. Data held in original documentation media are filtered, transcribed and upgraded into new composite datasets [*PE18 Datasets*] that refer to earlier stages of research (creating a chain of successive and interconnected references allowing the iteration from the interpretation to the documentation evidence and the material residues that support it, e.g. stratigraphic group is made by several individual contexts) [*I5 Inference Making*].

- Several of these inferential steps that employ parts of generated datasets are eventually synthesised into a comprehensive narrative that covers multiple aspects of excavation research and site history. The final narrative is reflected in the publication report [*E33 Linguistic object*] of the excavation and references all aggregated and re-structured data [*PE18 Datasets*].

Figure 16 provides a graphical representation of this process.

Figure 16: Conceptual representation of the entities and relationships of intra-site investigation activities.

5.2 Main entities of the excavation process

This section describes the main entities involved in the excavation research workflow and the correspondent classes of the AO-Cat model and the CIDOC CRM family proposed for their encoding.

Datasets

Datasets are digital objects containing information held in different documentation media. A dataset usually contains some form of fieldwork documentation or a structured description which is the result of study/analysis/interpretation activities. Each fieldwork, analysis, grouping or other interpretation event can generate more than one dataset or different facets of the same dataset (e.g. lists of excavation units vs stratigraphic groupings). They can be typically generated automatically using relevant software or manually by scholars, for example as resulting from the specific observations or interpretations made by them during fieldwork. Secondary/derived datasets can be generated in subsequent stages of the (post-)excavation investigation (e.g. stratigraphic grouping during post-excavation study, material analysis). These should maintain their reference to subsequent alterations all the way down to the original documentation and form part of a data lineage to allow for “competing” interpretations or alternative data groupings to be included in the excavation archive.

Datasets can be composed of single files, sets of documents or folders, compressed archives, databases and so on. The format and the content of the files included in the datasets can vary significantly according to the workflow by which they were generated: e.g. they can contain numerical values resulting from measurements, graphic representations, images, 3D models, textual descriptions. [*AO_Data_Resource; E73 Information Object; D9 Data Object; PE18 Dataset*]

Devices and Software

Mechanical or digital instruments used to document the archaeological investigation and compile spatial or analytical measurements. Being very specific tools, this kind of objects are usually associated with specific types of documentation and involve the use of specific software. One or more devices and software can be used through separate stages of processing to create a dataset. Certain aspects/details regarding the data production/processing workflows or device settings during data capture should be included. [*D8 Digital Device; D14 Software*]

Observable entities

All kinds of observable entities that are generated during archaeological fieldwork. These can be defined as part of the specific archaeological procedures or methodologies followed during fieldwork (e.g. an excavation unit, a surface) or intended analysis (e.g. a sample) or simply encountered (e.g. a feature or a find). These can be specified by type into sub-categories (e.g. investigation units, study objects, study features, samples and surfaces). [*AO_Object; S15 Observable Entity*]

Investigation units

Designated and discrete units of investigation across the excavation space. They refer to the tangible or intangible spatial imprint of the excavation process at a given location. They denote an activity of excavation, documented as a coherent set of actions of progressively recording and/or removing

matter from a pre-specified location under specific rules or procedures. These can follow the stratigraphy of the site or take an arbitrary form, removing substantial volumes of soil matrix or not. Their documentation includes data about the work carried out, the characteristics of the matter removed and its inclusions, their topological association with previous or subsequent units etc. [*AO_Object; S15 Observable Entities as a result of A1 Excavation Process Unit*].

Surfaces

Physical features that are created as part of the excavation process. They can reflect stratigraphic interfaces, arbitrary stratigraphic subdivisions, the revealed area of a trench at some point during excavation, the exposed trench section, the pre-excavation trench topography. They have a certain stability of form at the time of documentation that can be associated with a reference space (e.g. the north section of the trench). They are usually documented as to their geometry, inclusions and characteristics by photographs, drawings or 3D models. [*AO_Object; S20 Rigid Physical Feature*]

Study Objects

Moveable artefacts as groups or individuals as well as parts of them retrieved during fieldwork (e.g. a coin) or as part of a sample processing procedure (e.g. pieces of charcoal), including archaeological finds, fragments of frescoes, statues, reliefs, seeds, bones, molluscs etc. It is of particular importance to keep track of the origin and provenance of these objects and materials, the conditions under which they were encountered or retrieved from their original contexts. [*AO_Object; E18 Physical Thing; E19 Physical Object; E20 Biological Object; E22 Human-Made Object*]

Study Features

Immovable artefacts or parts of them revealed or retrieved during excavation, including architectural elements etc. It is important to keep track of the origin and provenance of these objects and materials and the conditions under which they were encountered in their original contexts. [*AO_Object; E18 Physical Thing; E26 Physical Feature; E25 Human-Made Feature*]

Samples

Physical portions of matter intended to be representative for the objects or the soil matrix environment to be analysed. They usually include: sediments, artefact parts, portions or sets of inorganic materials, fluids and organic materials e.g., bones, tissues etc. Provenance information is fundamental also for samples. Preserving a persistent link between a sample and the artefact from which it was extracted is equally important. [*AO_Object; S13 Sample*]

Archaeological Excavation

Any systematic excavation is organised around a set of observation, management, analytical and interpretive activities. These activities (or practices) are distinct, but at the same time directly related to each other, as each one may be supplemented or used in conjunction with others (e.g. the use of a find in a detailed study, presupposes its discovery, cleaning, cataloguing, taxonomic identification, relative dating etc, while its very inclusion in an analytic procedure may cancel, confirm or extend

many of the above). An archaeological excavation can be divided into different but interrelated sub-activities:

- a) fieldwork, where primary recording and interpretation takes place;
- b) analytic studies prepared for each individual set of excavated material or related observations;
- c) grouping activities that primarily refer to stratigraphic analysis but in a more generic understanding can refer to the consolidation of fragmentary observations into sets of interpretive significance (e.g. from a feature, to a house, to an occupation phase)
- d) the creation of a site narrative which transforms the overall observations of the excavation into knowledge about the past and is related to the ways of narration and communication of the research results.

This separation allows for a more structured analysis of the excavation microcosm as different datasets are generated or restructured among these activities. Actors in each sub-activity take on different roles by participating in individual tasks that serve the course of the entire archaeological project. [AO_Activity, but more generic; A9 Archaeological Excavation, E7 Activity]

Excavation recording

Specific activities relevant to the excavation process include the removal of earth, the retrieval of buried objects or features, the extraction of samples, the identification or artificial carving of surfaces, the descriptive and geometric documentation of all things encountered during this process using a set of documentation media and equipment. Fieldwork operations are often composed of a series of precisely defined procedures, often performed according to an already established methodological protocol (i.e. excavation guide). Fieldwork operations may change in times or over time due to different equipment employed (e.g. excavation machinery, documentation devices), unpredicted conditions (e.g. site flooding), methodological decisions (e.g. preferences of stratigraphic vs arbitrary excavation at places or the opposite). [AO_Activity, but more generic; S4 Observation]

Analysis

Specific activities consisting of scientific observations and measurements performed on objects or sets of objects or samples usually by means of specific instruments, in specific places (e.g. fieldwork, laboratory) at a given time. They can occur during fieldwork (e.g. magnetic susceptibility measurements), though they are usually associated with the bulk or selective processing and study of the retrieved material from the archaeological site (e.g. typological study of pottery, morphological study of lithics, quantification of flotation inclusions, petrographic analysis/XRF of selected pottery sherds etc). Each analytical procedure employs specific methodologies, comprises a series of precisely defined procedures, generates new datasets based on the material included and is usually summarised in a report. It may be of particular importance to document this set of events as a process that can change due to the participation of different actors, equipment or methodologies. [AO_Activity, but more generic; S4 Observation, S3 Measurement by Sampling]

Grouping

Specific activities aiming to re-aggregate the parts of the archaeological site that have been discretely retrieved and separately documented into meaningful sets that are associated physically (e.g. sherds into vessels), spatially (e.g. parts of a road in different trenches), chronologically (e.g. all objects recorded in 2001) or interpretively (e.g. pottery into ceramic assemblages by type, features into a house etc). The creation of each group is achieved by applying archaeological inferential reasoning (e.g. sherds of similar decoration into a pottery assemblage) or methodological procedures (e.g. Harris matrix rules). [*AO_Activity; A6 Group Declaration Event; I5 Inference making*].

Site narrative

Specific activities aiming to transform structured sets of data into a textual narrative that:

summarises or reviews different aspects of the archaeological investigation,

employs generated datasets and documentation media to convert archaeological observations made during fieldwork or at a later stage during post-excavation study into a historical narrative that pertains to past lifestyles and social practices. This is achieved through an argumentation process that associates empirical and processed (aggregated) archaeological observations as reflected in the compiled datasets/documentation media with existing background knowledge, i.e. scientific knowledge base, comparative and reference data.

The site narrative is crystallised in the form of a site report and usually includes a summarised facet of different generated datasets, accompanied by representative and curated illustrative material. [*AO_Activity; I5 Inference making*]

Site report

It reflects and summarises the results of excavations in a composite textual form. The report often includes structured, selected and curated sets of data that reference existing primary or derived datasets. [*AO_Object; E33 Linguistic Object*]

Archaeological location

The site where the archaeological excavation takes place. It denotes the entire site, but it can be subdivided into areas of investigation (e.g. trenches, test-pits). These can be spatially defined using predetermined points based on the pre-existing topographic grid. However, during the excavation they can be expanded or integrated with neighbouring ones adopting an open excavation strategy. [*E27 Site, E53 Place*]

Actors

Institutions, groups and people involved in various ways and with different roles in the activities of an intra-site investigation. Their roles could be alternating according to the activity in which they participate (e.g. an excavator could also be a lithics expert, an organisation could organise fieldwork and employ lab facilities for the conduct of specific analysis) [*AO-Agent, AO-Group, AO-Person; E39 Actor, E74 Group, E40 Legal Body, E21 Person*]

Projects

Collaborative initiatives, undertaken over a period of time by teams of actors with the intention of performing a defined program entailing the support of fieldwork documentation, subsequent study, analysis, interpretation and research result communication. [*PE35 Project*]

Metadata and their function for data retrieval

Some entities of this application profile are designed for data discovery, both in the ARIADNE Catalog and through specific interfaces explicitly developed for querying intra-site data; others are more descriptive and designed to provide additional information on each dataset once it has been compiled. Datasets are linked to specific activities in order to differentiate between fieldwork documentation, analytic procedures, grouping processes and interpretive statements.

In particular, the metadata relating to these basic entities provide criteria for the fast retrieval of datasets according to their type (the unit/object/feature/sample/surface in question), the level of interpretation, the project under which a group of scientific activities took place.

Descriptive data, useful once the datasets have been identified, provide further details about the actors involved and the specific information of the datasets, including their format, content, accessibility, rights.

5.3 Implementing the Excavation Application Profile

Excavation research has been at the forefront of archaeological data interoperability activities. This is understandable as it still provides the principal process for scientific data collection and interpretive reasoning in the archaeological domain. Data recording systems and methodologies with the aspiration of standardising the excavation process have appeared even before the digital turn in the discipline (e.g. MoLAS, Harris Matrix, J.-C. Gardin), followed by numerous digital documentation systems and underlying data models (e.g. IDEA, ArchéoDATA, IADB, SYSAND, Intrasis). The advent of semantic modelling was recognized as a way to align different documentation data resources and this had been most apparent in the interest of archaeologists to employ CIDOC CRM and provide domain specific implementations or facets. As part of the increased focus on digital archaeological data preservation, sharing and reuse, CRMarchaeo has been developed specifically to support archaeological data management during excavation projects to be followed by several extensions (such as CRMba and others) that interface excavation related activities to a greater or lesser extent (like building archaeology).

In spite of the general agreement that excavation datasets cannot be fully exploited, unless they can be combined together or connected with wider scale archaeological research data bodies, so far it has proved very difficult to integrate different excavation datasets. Still very few examples of interoperable datasets are out there and this has greatly to do with the complexity of excavation data archives, which are compiled with different tools and methodologies and for different research purposes, employ distinct conceptual descriptions at variable granularities, can often be unfinished or open-ended and may be linked to all sorts of digital data types, each with its own complicated production workflow.

Although CRMarchaeo has provided increased expressiveness, the fact that excavation research interfaces with several archaeological areas depending on research stage, requires concepts from multiple CRM family models to achieve modelling coherence. This obviously increases implementation difficulties as modellers have to navigate within an ever expanding universe of concepts, properties and inheritances, while multiple implementation paths with complementary concepts means that there are more than one ways to express certain relationships.

As a result, we are still some way from a common semantic description of the excavation universe. In this respect, it was realised that rather than attempting to create yet another AP for excavation data modelling, which could potentially add confusion, a better strategy would be to bring together already existing modelling attempts that try to model the excavation domain, compare and find their similarities and differences. Working in this direction helped us communicate our internal conceptualizations of the excavation domain and its data using a shared language. The organisation of a virtual workshop on “Semantic mapping of archaeological excavation data”²⁰ was also key towards this end, as it provided an opportunity to discuss individual experiences, contextualise the current state of research, understand available options with respect to tools that can help the modelling process and increase awareness of the benefits of conceptual data modelling in wider archaeological audiences and stakeholders.

Five research areas were highlighted as having potential to consolidate and coordinate the excavation data modelling community, and in particular:

- a) **Models**, by developing those that have the capacity to describe the application domain consistently (e.g., CRMarchaeo)
- b) **Questions**, by identifying meaningful queries that can be posed on integrated archaeological excavation datasets
- c) **Methods**, by comparing existing excavation modelling examples, establishing modelling patterns and basic application scenarios, encouraging digital pedagogy and ontological thinking
- d) **Workflows and Tools**, by employing the major software tools that can be used in ontological modelling and data mapping and addressing their potential expansion or combination.
- e) **Learning and training**, by providing educational material, digital facilities and teaching opportunities for semantic modelling.

With respect to **models**, the evolution of CIDOC CRM has allowed domain specific definitions that are more successful in capturing domain-specific meaning, such as CRMarchaeo, CRMba and CRMinf. However, the fact that an archaeological excavation is a multi-level process, happening on multiple fields, using different methodologies and documentation media or tools, illustrates the difficulties still encountered in its complete description. We found that the meaning of several real-world entities or their documentation proxies can be mapped to different model concepts depending on the research context or stage. For example, what may be identified as a *feature* during excavation, may be referred to as a *stratigraphic interface* that separates stratigraphic entities, as a *filled morphological building*

²⁰ All presentations and the report have been made available through Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7112917>) and the respective page at the ARIADNEplus website (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/semantic-mapping-of-excavation-data/>).

section in architectural studies, as a belief to be a neolithic wall part in interpretive statements, as a *digital data object* that substitutes the original physical object in post-excavation research (Figure 17). In this respect, we need to distinguish between different contexts or stages of the excavation process and establish common descriptions that facilitate a basic level of agreement.

Figure 17. The CIDOC CRM family of models and an example of complementary domain specific descriptions of an excavation feature.

The possibility for the multiple instantiation of concepts, i.e. the inclusion of multiple conceptual tags for the same object, was acknowledged as a useful approach for mitigating these problems. In addition, it was recognised that the more specific and all-encompassing a description of the excavation process gets, the more difficult it becomes to stick to baseline descriptions. In this respect, there are many occasions where datasets are partly compatible with CIDOC CRM descriptions and employ custom ontologies or complementary semantic standards (e.g. Dublin Core) to better fit existing excavation methodologies or dissemination needs. This is not necessarily a drawback, as data interoperability is required to those information fields that make sense to be connected.

To understand what we really need when searching aggregated excavation datasets, as an additional step, we need to explore the potential **questions** that researchers would formulate in order to retrieve existing reusable data. The formulation of questions can reveal what makes sense to ask multiple excavation datasets and what each question involves in terms of the respective syntax. By posing questions and analysing their syntax we may succeed in identifying a minimum baseline for useful excavation data descriptions. This exercise can also provide minimal and economical descriptions that can be standardised and re-used in new data integration processes. Finally, it may help in figuring out what an overall excavation domain description would mean in terms of basic concepts and linkages and how could these then relate to more exhaustive descriptions of the excavation domain or other related sub-domains.

With respect to **methods**, we advocate the purposeful bringing together of data mapping examples to explore similarities and differences, compare their scope and meaning and decide upon standardised semantic descriptions or semantic data “patterns”. Equally, the analysis of existing modelling examples and implementations has the potential to identify such modelling scenarios and provide a closer understanding of the evolution of the respective CIDOC CRM extensions. Such a strategy can obviously start from core or generic entities involved in the excavation process and subsequently be extended to cover more specific meanings.

In all cases, these data patterns can then be documented and made available for use within the community as standardised data modelling recipes in the form of a modular data description building process or a modelling cookbook. This approach can foster a less challenging familiarisation with semantic modelling processes for domain experts, increasing the possibilities for a greater number of compatible implementations. It can also provide critical studies of model definitions in an applied form and identify the problematic areas that require further development with respect to their ontological integrity or their compatibility with different archaeological excavation methods and interpretive procedures.

With respect to **workflows and tools**, several main pathways were identified for semantic mapping.

- a) Within the ARIADNEplus project a data mapping workflow is based on the X3ML toolkit, which comprises a set of small, open-source software components for information integration. These include the X3ML Mapping Definition Language (<https://github.com/isl/x3ml/blob/master/docs/x3ml-language.md>), the 3M Mapping Memory Manager (<https://demos.isl.ics.forth.gr/3m/>), the X3ML Engine (<https://github.com/isl/x3ml>) and the RDF Visualiser (<https://demos.isl.ics.forth.gr/RDFV-Demo/>). Together these tools can be used within a complete workflow for transforming XML exports of datasets/databases into CIDOC CRM compatible RDFs. This process can be combined with tools for achieving vocabulary homogenization such as the Vocabulary Matching Tool (VMT) by the University of Wales (accessed from within the ARIADNEplus VRE services and <https://heritagedata.org/vocabularyMatchingTool/>), which maps concepts to Getty’s Art and Architecture Thesaurus and PeriodO - <https://perio.do>, which is used to match chronological periods with absolute date ranges.
- b) Under the MASA consortium a workflow that covers the data-lifecycle of archaeological excavation data includes several steps and multiple tools, for dataset cleansing (OpenRefine - <https://openrefine.org>), ontology structuration and vocabulary alignment into an interoperable dataset (e.g. MySQL, PostgreSQL) that is mapped (Protégé-Ontop, (<https://protege.stanford.edu> & <https://ontop-vkg.org>) and validated (SHACL, <https://shacl-play.sparna.fr/play/>) as an RDF TripleStore with a SPARQL endpoint (<https://sparnatural.eu>). The generic backbone allows the linkage of several excavation datasets into an interoperable data pool at the expense of the specificities of each dataset.
- c) Another approach - useful for aligning finalised or closed datasets - attempts the direct creation of RDFs from spreadsheets or databases. Datasets are analysed and rearranged into sets of spreadsheets or data tables that correspond with a combination of semantic standards. Tables are then integrated within a database (Postgres) that allows further data structuring (e.g. URI addition). Afterwards, semantic tools (e.g. Karma, <https://usc-isi-i2.github.io/karma/>

or OntoRefine) are used for RDF creation. In many cases, though, similar processes that involve the alignment of several datasets with respect to both their transformation to a conceptual reference model and among themselves, may need to be complemented by decisions on what to include to the final deposition files, as well as significant manual data cleaning, conversion and alignment (e.g., the ADED project).

- d) A different route, showcased by the Archaeological Interactive Report (AIR) attempts to standardise the archaeological publication process by providing an extensive alignment of archaeological information fields with multiple semantic models. This solution standardises the entire informational potential of the publication platform data schema, to allow further data integration with data aggregators using RDFs.

Several other data mapping solutions exist in between or even outside these four main workflows. It seems that the current ecosystem of data modelling and knowledge organisation tools is far from standardised. Certain steps towards the further standardisation of certain workflows, the purposeful further development of selected tools by the archaeological community and the explanation of the benefits or overlaps of specific tool sets with actual examples is required.

Accordingly, **learning and training** should be given attention in order to attract further audience for building new or sharing existing semantically compatible archaeological excavation datasets. At the rookie level, the CIDOC CRM Game,²¹ either in the table or its online edition, can provide an entry point for domain experts who want to understand the mechanics and benefits of semantic structures. At a more intermediate level, the identification of excavation data modelling patterns (available in Annex B of the Archaeological Excavation Modelling Working Group internal ARIADNEplus report²²) will eventually comprise a cookbook for data modellers, allowing the creation of a kind of a marketplace for archaeological semantic data. At an even more advanced level, this marketplace can include data modelling examples and workflows, complemented by structured tutorials and targeted workshops. As discussed by many experts during the event, training in archaeological knowledge organisation may bring together different views of the excavation universe and even impact archaeological theory and data management methods.

5.4 The Paliambela Kolindros excavation data

The Paliambela Kolindros excavation dataset is the product of one of the first 3D GIS documentation workflows that included conceptual modelling using CIDOC CRM to describe data components. The integration of this excavation dataset within the ARIADNEplus infrastructure at the item-level has been a core incentive for participating in the consortium. The preparation of a partial and incomplete geospatial data archive for deposition has made numerous challenges apparent, some of which included the necessity to update existing semantic descriptions. Within the excavation modelling group, data modelling components have been produced and shared, while the final data mapping has tried to implement to a large degree some of the semantic patterns included in Annex B²³ and also experiment with multiple instantiation. Apart from the practical aspects of consolidating an

²¹ <https://www.cidoc-crm-game.org>.

²² See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377910>.

²³ *Ibidem*.

excavation dataset, this process has led to many realisations concerning the digitally assisted excavation documentation and reasoning, as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Data mapping example from the Paliambela Kolindros excavation project.

6 Implementing the ARIADNE Ontology

The construction of the ARIADNE Ontology, a complete ontological framework capable of expressing in detail the statements of the ARIADNE infrastructure and the information it aggregates, was one of the main goals of project activities. The ontology is conceived as a refinement of CIDOC CRM and arises from the harmonisation of AO-Cat and all the other application profiles developed by the project in a single integrated and modular ontological ecosystem for the modelling of all the information aggregated in ARIADNE.

From an implementation point of view, compatibility with the CIDOC CRM and with the other ARIADNE ontological models has always been considered as a fundamental criterion for evaluating the quality of each application profile developed in a specific domain. This has materialised, for example, in the search and reuse of entities already existing in other ontologies and in evaluating the definition of new classes or properties only when strictly necessary for the needs of a specific domain. The mechanism of inheritance and reuse of existing entities has been applied in the majority of cases for domains strictly connected with pure archaeological research, for which the CIDOC CRM family has proved to be perfectly able to deal with the many needs highlighted during the analysis phases.

In particular CRMarchaeo, the extension of CIDOC CRM created to support the archaeological excavation process, has demonstrated its potential for information regarding excavation and other related archaeological activities, the collection and study of materials, their cataloguing and archiving. The model, in its latest releases, provides all the necessary tools to manage and integrate existing documentation in order to formalise knowledge derived from observations performed during the archaeological activity.

CRMarchaeo allows the ontological description of physical arrangements of archaeological stratigraphy and the events that led to its formation, and to the description of the nature and shape of stratigraphic units. It also permits the semantic description of human remains and artefacts found within the investigated area in order to define stratigraphic sequences in chronological arrangement, perform space-time analysis of sites, and make inferences on the life, beliefs, behaviour and activities of the people who occupied the investigated areas in the past.

The model has evolved a lot in recent years, also thanks to the feedback provided by ARIADNE which has also proved to be fundamental for improving the effectiveness of CRMarchaeo in its application to complex archaeological records, such as those generated by fieldwork activities. Indeed, thanks to the great variety of application scenarios proposed by the various ARIADNE content providers, CRMarchaeo has been further enhanced and made able to overcome the differences resulting from the application of different excavation techniques and procedures established by different archaeological traditions and schools and to provide a unified view that can express common archaeological concepts, thus constituting a solid basis for the integration of datasets resulting from various investigation methodologies.

In more specific cases, as in those ARIADNE domains closely connected with heritage science (e.g., studies on ancient DNA, inorganic material, dating, etc.), it has become necessary to create new conceptual tools for the appropriate description of information such as the acquisition and study of

samples, analysis of objects and materials, encoding of scientific results and so on. As much as possible, the approach of reusing existing entities (such for instance those of CRMsci) was also applied in these cases, since the new models defined in specific domains were in turn reused in application profiles of domains that required similar entities, as in the case of CRMhs (developed for inorganic material and dating) which has been used for the encoding of scientific data generated by Environmental Archeology and Remote Sensing, or in the case of the application profile developed for bio-archaeology and ancient DNA, and used for the investigation of skeletons, bones and other biological remains in the domain of human burials..

The application of the ARIADNE Ontology also facilitates the use of strategies aimed at a more extensive semantic description of information. The multiple instantiation technique, used for example in complex datasets such as those of fieldwork activity, permits the description of multifaceted information by means of two or more classes, even derived from different ontologies. It is possible, for example, to describe archaeological entities such as instances of AO-Cat and CIDOC CRM classes at the same time, in order to give them different nuances, making them more detailed and ready to be used in different contexts. The Mapping Memory Manager (3M) tool provides extensive documentation of the use of this and other encoding techniques on real data, and the possibility, for researchers of the same domains, to reapply the same methodologies employed by the ARIADNE Ontology to their data.

As it is conceived and implemented, the ARIADNE Ontology is designed to be a complete, flexible and extremely articulated tool capable of achieving integration and establishing interoperability among aggregated data. It also provides the linguistic and axiomatic basis of the ARIADNE Knowledge Base, supports interoperability with other Linked Data datasets of the Cultural Heritage domain and defines the entities of the ARIADNE Catalogue and the domain-specific parts of the ARIADNE infrastructure.

7 Conclusions

The aim of WP4, and specifically of task 4.3, was to define conceptual models for the implementation of a deep integration between the aggregated data made findable and discoverable by ARIADNEplus, in order to encode them in standard formats and make them interoperable and reusable in different scenarios, in accordance with the FAIR principles. In the light of what was produced by the activities carried out by this work package (and in close collaboration with WP14), we can state that the results achieved have gone far beyond the expectations framed at the beginning of the project. Indeed, the development process of the application profiles and their systematisation as part of the general ARIADNE ontological framework have not only allowed the efficient and complete representation of the entire ARIADNE information ecosystem, but have also greatly contributed to the advancement of research in the field of the development of ontologies and conceptual models for cultural heritage. The different techniques and procedures adopted to build the application profiles and make them effective tools, particularly suitable for expressing the various facets and the meaning of their data in all their complexity, has demonstrated the creative capacity of all the partners involved in this activity. The procedure was rigorous in every phase, from the examination of existing entities, to evaluating their effective semantic extension and applicability to specific information, to the definition of new ones where the need arose to have more adequate conceptual tools. The great variety in the types of archaeological data and in their mutual relationships have required innovative and specific strategies to model all types of data and achieve their deep and effective integration.

Of particular note was the development of the AO-Cat, a completely new standard that allowed us to construct the ARIADNE Catalogue in an effective and straightforward way, and to achieve an outstanding level of integration of over three million archaeological resources encompassing all sub-domains. The AO-Cat has proved to be perfectly adequate and sufficient for modelling data on palaeo-anthropology (subtask 4.4.1), maritime and underwater archeology (subtask 4.4.11) and for most of the information in the domains of environmental archeology (subtask 4.4.3) and public archaeological finds (subtask 4.4.7), in which the extensive use of controlled vocabularies to assign specific concepts to each of the defined instances has also allowed to reach a particularly extensive level of integration. The fact that a slightly modified version of the AO-Cat is now proving itself fit for purpose for data aggregation of maritime heritage data drawn from all of the constituent nations of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland demonstrates its applicability to projects beyond ARIADNE. AO-Cat has also proved to be efficient in combination with the extensions of the CIDOC CRM ecosystem used for field survey information (subtask 4.4.6 in combination with CRMarchaeo), standing structures (subtask 4.4.9, in interaction with CRMba) and inscriptions (subtask 4.4.13 together with CRMtex). In some cases it was sufficient to combine AO-Cat with a specialised service, such as that of spatio-temporal data (subtask 4.4.10) set up for interoperability of geographical information, to achieve optimal integration without any need to define additional dedicated conceptual tools.

Among the new models, in addition to AO-Cat, the development of the application profile for scientific data (CRMhs, for subtasks 4.4.4 and 4.4.5) and for bio-archaeology and ancient DNA (subtask 4.4.2) was also of considerable interest. These are two entirely new models, harmonised with each other, and devoted to the study of the specific problems of heritage science. The classes and properties

introduced by these models have also proved to be of great use in other subdomains. In fact, one of the most interesting strategies adopted in the development phase was the reuse of models previously defined in ARIADNEplus, (CRMhs and aDNA in particular) for the definition of subsequent application profiles, such as those for remote sensing (subtask 4.4.8) and burials (4.4.14). In this case, the conceptual foundations and the logic with which the reused entities had previously been defined in the original ontologies have also been taken up and adapted to the rationales of the new models. A very sophisticated case was that of fieldwork activity (task 4.4.12), where the complexity of the domain and of the multiple events and activities (not only archaeological) that it involves required the deployment of most of the ARIADNE Ontology models alongside CRMarchaeo for the development of the application profile, as evidenced by the case study presented in Section 5. The ability to describe in detail the entities of such a multifaceted domain certainly represents the best proof of the quality of the ARIADNE Ontology and its conceptual components.

The definition of such an assorted and well-orchestrated set of ontological models is an extraordinary achievement for a project like ARIADNEplus which has put integration and interoperability at the heart of its research programme. Beyond their immediate usefulness for the construction of the ARIADNE semantic data space, the importance of this development work lies in the ability to conceptually model the infinite facets of a complex domain such as that of archeology and of all that revolves around it. This kind of activity required mastery of every aspect of the various research domains and an exceptional capacity for abstraction and concreteness at the same time, as demonstrated by the partners involved. The application profiles are innovative tools, ready to be used also in external contexts, as an effective standard for the information of other research domains. The ARIADNE Ontology is squarely placed in the family of CIDOC CRM ontologies, which it enriches and with which it forms a synergistic system for modelling any type of information produced by the domains of Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science. In conclusion, the activities carried out by WP4 to build the application profiles of the individual research domains and implement the ARIADNE Ontology have proved to be extremely fruitful, thanks to the close collaboration and contribution that all the partners involved have provided, and to their constant commitment to achieving this fundamental goal.

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